

Coordination Plan

D5.1 Detailed Work Plan & Quality Assurance Guidelines

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Technical References

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- 1 PU = Public
 PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
 RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
 CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

V	Date	Beneficiary	Author
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V0.3	31-03-2023	WR integrated comments	Rosalie van Dam

Summary

Deliverable 5.1 “Detailed Work Plan and Quality Assurance Guidelines” is an operational plan for executing the first two years of the BIOTraCes project. This work plan is designed to facilitate the organization of the project and the implementation of the project activities. This document specifies the project and organization structure, and addresses also our way of working as a project, in terms of roles, communication and decision making processes. It also details the official reporting phases and monitoring. This workplan can help to correctly comply with contractual obligations as foreseen in the Grant Agreement with the European Commission and the Consortium Agreement. At the same time, it also addresses our transformative way of working and the day-to-day activities with the final objective of maximising the Project's results and achievements.

Overall, this plan is intended as a living document to be further developed and adjusted as the project develops. Moreover, the adjusted version will also result in D5.2, an operational plan for the last two years of the BIOTraCes project.

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1 PROJECT OVERVIEW

The main goal of this work plan and guidelines is to support and guide the BIOTraCes Work Package (WP) leaders, the Task Leaders (TL) and all contributors to manage and implement the project. The Grant Agreement which includes the project plan drafted by the consortium and Consortium Agreement are strict guidance and therefore providing most input for this work plan. At the same time, it also addresses our transformative way of working and the day-to-day activities with the final objective of maximising the Project's results and achievements.

1.1 Project Objectives

BIOTraCes develops knowledge, tools and novel approaches that enable transformative changes (TC), necessary for achieving a nature positive society. The project aims to contribute to more inclusive, effective and just public policies, local strategies and corporate concerns on biodiversity aligned with the European Green Deal and SDGs.

BIOTraCes aims at **co-producing relevant knowledge in order to develop approaches and strategies that contribute to transformative changes that are necessary to preserve and restore biodiversity in Europe**. By developing a Theory of Transformative Change (ToTC) the project will enhance understanding of the fundamental roles played by, and connections among, values, power and behaviour, in order to address the underlying (indirect) drivers of biodiversity decline. This objective will be achieved by building upon principles of *pluralising, empowering, politicising and embedding* - developing capacities for innovation and fostering transformative (i.e., adaptive, plural and equitable) governance approaches to achieve just and nature-positive societies.

Specific objectives:

O1: Understand the role of diverse values, knowledge systems, power, and behaviour in transformative biodiversity approaches. BIOTraCes will develop a Theory of Transformative Change (ToTC) that relates plurality of (cultural, religious, social, economic) values and power (lock-ins and leverage) to behaviour (practices, actions, choices and decisions) of individuals and groups (consumers, producers and enabling players in civil society, science, economy and policy), in relation to the underlying drivers of biodiversity decline.

O2: Demonstrate practices and key principles of transformative change for nature-positive societies. BIOTraCes will engage with, describe and analyse examples

of transformative niches (empowering) in sectors with a high impact on biodiversity by means of case studies in eight EU member states.

O3: Develop strategies to aid transformative (i.e., integrative, adaptive, inclusive and pluralistic) governance approaches. We will compare, assess and innovate decision-making tools and methodologies for integrating biodiversity into public and private decision-making (embedding), overcoming obstacles for behavioural change in biodiversity innovations and at the same time recognising the need for inclusive approaches and taking into consideration the plurality of contexts, cultures and values (empowering, pluralising).

O4: Contribute to propelling transformative changes for biodiversity, local to global. Building upon, collaborating with and exchanging with related projects on biodiversity and transformative change will expand the reach of BIOTraCes.

1.2 Project structure

To achieve the objectives mentioned in the previous section, BIOTraCes designed five work packages:

WP	Work Package Title	Lead Participant
1	Conceptual Framework for Theory of Transformative Change	8 - UT
2	Case studies of transformative biodiversity practices	7- UNICT
3	Strategies and Approaches for Just Transformative Changes	2 - UGOT
4	Impact Creation: Communication, Dissemination, Engagement, Exploitation	10 - ESCI
5	Project Coordination and Interproject collaboration	1 - WR

WP1 Conceptual Framework for Theory of Transformative Change provides conceptual and methodological inputs for the project as a whole, ensures ethical and inclusive research throughout the project, supports action research in the case studies carried out in WP2 and will develop BIOTraCes' Theory of Transformative Change. The tasks are developed to prepare for the analyses that will be carried out in several layers in WP2 and to enable the synthesis into strategies and approaches in WP3.

WP2 Case studies of Transformative Biodiversity Practices focuses on the fieldwork in the nine case studies in which action research and co-production of knowledge will take place between research partners and stakeholders in the transformative biodiversity innovations. The WP is organized with a task for case study coordination and approach and

two tasks that represent two scales and foci of analysis, starting with action research in cooperation with local initiatives addressing the transformative biodiversity innovations analysis, and then scale up the results in a social-ecological system analysis which will address the wider context of these initiatives. In addition, a task is included for joint experimentation with transformative interventions, as well as monitoring and evaluation.

WP3 Strategies and Approaches for Just Transformative Changes towards Nature-positive Societies provides actionable knowledge, strategies and approaches for initiating, accelerating and upscaling these changes. It will compare, assess and innovate policy and governance approaches for integrating biodiversity into public and private decision-making, enhancing behavioural change and at the same time recognising the need for taking inclusive approaches. The combination of a bottom up (from case studies) and top down (institutional) approach will identify opportunities for leverage and upscaling. Further tasks will address different 'accents' in strategies and approaches: Strategies that translate the identified opportunities for leverage into action and accelerating transformative change; Strategies for learning, co-creation, consultation and dialogue; Innovative thinking for just and effective governance; and an analysis and governance recommendations of biodiversity interdependencies of SDGs.

WP4 Impact Creation: Communication, Dissemination, Engagement and Exploitation aims to raise awareness, inform and engage with various stakeholders and target groups. By various networking and communication activities it will transfer results, strategies, knowledge on biodiversity-related innovations and transformative change in society, policy, science and the policy-science interface. Moreover, WP4 develops exploitation strategies to ensure that the project will have a long-lasting impact.

WP5 Project Coordination and Inter-project collaboration is to coordinate the project as a whole, to facilitate the project team in various ways, to ensure good data management and build on, initiate and shape various forms of inter-project collaboration. As a result of the approach of the project, WP5 is more than Project Coordination and will also entail:

- **facilitating reflexivity and learning** to improve the project members transdisciplinary thinking on transformative change, discuss their role and positionality as researchers in the field, and co-design ways of working together and contribute to smooth collaboration within the consortium and with societal partners.
- **installing and taking on the input of an Influencer and Stakeholder Board** of change agents of policy, business as well as social, religious and cultural leaders that will think along with the partners, reflect on results, help in embedding the results in a pluralized way and in accelerating the impact of this project.
- actively and substantially **connecting and working together with relevant European Research projects and science-policy interfaces** to build on and move forward on knowledge, strategies and approaches for initiating, accelerating and upscaling just transformative changes towards nature-positive societies.

Each workpackage is organized in several tasks, see for the overview of tasks the figure below.

SEP Figure 2: Work packages and tasks in the project and how they interrelate.

2 PROJECT GOVERNANCE

2.1 Project governance structure

In figure 3, the general overview of the project governance is shown. The project governance addresses both how we work together within the project and the way we manage and decide within this project.

Figure 3: BIOTraCes' governance structure

The following bodies are relevant for project management and decision making; each has specific roles and competencies.

The General Assembly (GA) is the decision-making body of the Consortium and comprises one representative of each Party who has responsibilities for conducting the Project. The Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the General Assembly, unless decided otherwise by the General Assembly. The General Assembly shall not deliberate and decide validly in meetings unless two-thirds (2/3) of its Members are present or represented (quorum).

The Work Package Leaders Group (WPLG) is the supervisory body for the execution of the Project, which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly. It is established to supervise the activities' state of progress as well as the timely fulfilment of milestones and deliverables of all WP's. WP leaders assist the project coordinator in

reporting duties to the EC within their competence. The WPLG consists of (at least) 1 representative of each WP-leading partner.

The Project Coordinator is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. More practically, the project coordinator is organised as follows:

- **Project Coordination Team**

The Project Coordination Team supports the Coordinator in the management of the Project. The coordination team consists of members of the lead partner of the consortium, Wageningen Research.

- **Project coordination core team**

- **Project coordinator** is the representative of the Coordinator, who is authorised to execute project management.
- **Project officer** ensures support for the project coordination team in terms of project meetings and support for administrative issues.
- **Other team members of the lead partner** ensure support for the project coordination team.

- **Project administration**

- **Project financial officer** is responsible for the financial reporting and monitoring of budget expenditures and provides partners with all necessary information and guidance in order to ensure that all costs incurred are in line with the Horizon Europe rules and provisions. Tracking the costs of the financial statements to be provided by each partner.
- **Project legal officer:** ensures the management of the Consortium Agreement as well as the Grant Agreement and leads the discussion on amendments and revisions of these Agreements, if necessary. Also, management of the distribution of funds among partners according to the rules established by the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

The Influencer and Stakeholder Board (ISB) will inspire and advise on project strategy and results and help with outreach and embedding in society, policy and science-policy interfaces. It does not have voting rights. The Influencer and Stakeholder Board consists of several (ca. 5) key players, who are in various ways influential and who are active in top positions on EU or global level concerning business, politics, religion, nature conservation and/or youth culture. The board will meet three times during the course of the four-year project. The Influencer and Stakeholder board will be installed to reflect on our research and to bring insights and ideas developed in the project further into their networks and contribute to our mutual wish for impact and change.

WP Leaders, Task Leaders and project members:

Leaders are assigned to every WP. They will be responsible for ensuring the organization and implementation of tasks, deliverables and milestones for their specific work packages. The main tasks performed by WP and Task Leaders include: organising and chairing WP and task meetings; preparing reports and facilitating communication between partners involved in each WP, with the Coordinator and with other WP Leaders. WP leaders will also be responsible for promptly communicating to the Coordinator potential discrepancies and delays in the delivery of WP results and to report on progress of their WPs. Task Leaders are also identified and will be responsible for the timely implementation of the activities in their task. They will report to the WP Leader and make decisions related to the task, with the agreement of the WP Leader. Project members of all partners will be contributing to the project of BioTraCes concerning various activities and input in WPs and Tasks.

BIOTraCes consists of nine research partners, one communication and dissemination partner, and local societal partners in the 9 case studies.

- **Co-creation with societal partners:** The research partners will be carrying out action research and will be co-creating knowledge with local societal partners. One of the societal partners was able to become a formal partner (CEA -Spain), but as the other local partners are mostly citizens' initiatives and civil society organisations, their organisations cannot carry the administrative burden of becoming a full partner. To deal with that situation, per research partner financial provisions are made for the input, effort and the cooperation of the local societal partners.

Moreover, BIOTraCes will build on and connect to other research projects related to biodiversity and transformative change.

- **Connecting and working together with relevant European Research Projects and Science-Policy interfaces related to Biodiversity and Transformative change.** The project partners will continuously collaborate to create synergies and cooperate with other research projects and networks and initiatives concerning transformative change for biodiversity with the objective to build on and move forward on knowledge, strategies and approaches accelerating and upscaling just transformative changes towards nature-positive societies.

The BIOTraCes team will 'practice what they preach' and will actively address reflexivity and learning among the partners.

- **Reflexivity and learning as a team.** With action research and by means of theory development and analysis we aim to contribute to transformative change, but does that mean for our roles, skills and ways as researchers. We will pay attention to transdisciplinary thinking on transformative change of the project members themselves and for our collaboration. What do the principles of pluralising, empowering, politicising and embedding also mean for our project and how can we be transformative ourselves.

The organizational structure of the Work Packages and their leads, the tasks and their leads are displayed in the following Gantt Chart:

Detailed Work Plan & Quality Assurance Guidelines

BIOTraCes Gantt Chart		D = Deliverables M = Milestones																																															
		Year 1												Year 2												Year 3												Year 4											
WP ID	WP Title	Q1 Q2 Q3 Q4																																															
		1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24 25 26 27 28 29 30 31 32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40 41 42 43 44 45 46 47 48																																															
WP1	Conceptual Framework for Theory of Transformative Change (UT)																																																
T1.1	Towards Grounded Theories of Transformative Change (TOTC) (UT)																																																
T1.2	Research Ethics and Principles for Equitable Participation (UT)																																																
T1.3	Tools and Approaches for Action Research, Participatory Monitoring and Learning																																																
T1.4	Theories and Methods for Transformative Biodiversity innovations Analysis (UNICT)																																																
T1.5	Theories and Methods for Social Ecological Systems Analysis (BC3)																																																
T1.6	Theories and Methods to Disclose the Underlying Causes of Biodiversity Loss (CER)																																																
T1.7	Methods for Synthesis and Comparative Analysis (WR)																																																
WP2	Case Studies of Transformative Biodiversity Practices (UNICT)																																																
T2.1	Case Study Coordination and Approach (UNICT)																																																
T2.2	Transformative Biodiversity Innovations Analysis (UNICT)																																																
T2.3	Social-Ecological System Analysis (BC3)																																																
T2.4	Development and Testing of Interventions (CES)																																																
WP3	Strategies and Approaches for Just Transformative Changes (UGOT)																																																
T3.1	Opportunities for Leverage and Upscaling (BC3)																																																
T3.2	Strategies for Public, Private and Civil Society Actors to Initiate and Accelerate																																																
T3.3	Strategies for Learning, Co-creation Consultation, Dialogue (WR)																																																
T3.4	Innovative Thinking for Just and Effective Governance (CES)																																																
T3.5	Biodiversity Interdependencies of SDGs (MRU)																																																
WP4	Impact creation: Communication, Dissemination, Engagement and Exploitation (ESCI)																																																
T4.1	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy (DECS) Master Plan (ESCI)																																																
T4.2	Dissemination, Engagement, Clustering and Networking Activities (UT)																																																
T4.3	Communication Activities (ESCI)																																																
T4.4	Exploitation Roadmap and IP Management (WR)																																																
WP5	Project Coordination and Inter-project collaboration (WR)																																																
T5.1	Contract, Financial and Administrative Management (WR)																																																
T5.2	Project Coordination and Quality Assurance (WR)																																																
T5.3	Reflexivity and Learning as A Team (UNICT)																																																
T5.4	Involvement Influencer and Stakeholder Board (WR)																																																
T5.5	Data Management (MRU)																																																
T5.6	Inter-Project Collaboration (WR)																																																

2.2 Meeting procedure

Whether virtual or physical, a meeting is convened by the chairperson (WP leads, task leaders or project Coordination Team) who will also determine the location in consultation with the foreseen attendees. For major meetings, the Project Coordination Team will provide support and keep track of the action items. If the Project Coordination Team is not present, it is the responsibility of the chairperson to prepare and distribute the action items. Partners may also participate in physical meetings by teleconference if the facilities are available. Minutes should highlight main decisions taken and action points

General Assembly Meetings

The chairperson shall convene ordinary meetings of the General Assembly 4 times a year: 3 times online and 1 physical. The physical meetings will be held at various partners. The Live Kick Off meeting was held in Wageningen. The Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the General Assembly, unless decided otherwise by the General Assembly.

Work Package Leader meetings

The project coordinator will organise online meetings with all WP leaders four times per year (to be scheduled ca. 1 month before project meetings with all partners). Generally, these WP-leader meetings will be about updates on the process and content of the WP's and the relations between the WP's, and about discussing together what of and how these issues should be discussed with the whole project team (general assembly) a few weeks later.

Work Package meetings

Work package meetings are held within work packages online or hybrid with the aim of facilitating a greater exchange of knowledge, contributing to the deliverables and milestones and better mutual updating. WP leads can convene meetings with other partners whenever required.

Task meetings

Task meetings are held within work packages online or hybrid with the aim of facilitating a greater exchange of knowledge, contributing to the deliverables and milestones and better mutual updating. Task leads can convene meetings with other partners whenever required. Tasks which will require meetings are for example:

- *Reflexivity and learning as a team.*

A particular task will concern reflexivity and learning as a team, which will provide for meetings every 8-10 weeks concerning specific subjects, by encouraging intervision and transdisciplinary dialogue;

- *Working together with other international projects*

Another particular task concerns the connecting and cooperation with other relevant international Research projects on Transformative change for Biodiversity. This will result in meetings with project leaders and other relevant members of other projects. At the moment of writing an initiative is taken to form a cluster of a few Horizon Europe projects with working title "Values, Norms and Justice Working Group"

The Influencer and Stakeholder Board meetings will be held 3 times during the project and will take place in consultation with the members of ISB in combination with logical moments in the project. We aspire to also convene physical once or twice, but due to ecological and practical reasons, that might change to online.

3 PROJECT MANAGEMENT MANUAL

3.1 Project monitoring

WP5 is entrusted with project monitoring to ensure WPs progress and work plan consistency and interaction with other WPs. Project monitoring is led by the Project Coordinator in coordination with the Project Coordination Team. Within WP5 and in consultation with each WP, a task lead is to be appointed for each deliverable. In principle, this will be the WP lead unless agreed otherwise. This should enable WP5 to:

- monitor compliance of the Parties with their obligations under the Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement (Project Management Officer)
- keep the address list of Members and other contact persons updated and available (Project Management Officer)
- collect and review reports to verify their consistency before their submission, as well as other deliverables (including financial statements and related certification), including specific documents, requested documents to the Granting Authority (Project Manager)
- prepare the meetings, proposing decisions and preparing the agenda of General Assembly meetings, chairing the meetings, preparing the minutes of the meetings and monitoring the implementation of decisions taken at meetings (Project Coordination Team)
- transmit promptly documents and information connected with the Project to any other Party concerned (Project Coordination Team)
- administer the financial contribution of the Granting Authority and fulfil the financial tasks described in the Consortium Agreement (Finance Officer)
- provide, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims (Legal Officer)
- provide a copy of the Grant Agreement and its Annexes to the Associated Partners (Legal officer)

Monitoring will focus on the execution of the work plan of each of the WP, including their associated activities and respective deliverables in line with the periodic reporting requirements in months 18, 36, 48. This work plan is depicted in the Gantt chart on page 13.

3.2 Project reporting & Quality assurance

3.2.1 Deliverables

Each deliverable is submitted to the EC with preliminary approval obtained from the Project Coordinator. The BIOTraCes deliverables are strictly tied to the breakdown into Work Packages that constitutes the structure of the Project (see Gantt chart on page 13). Deliverables are generally technical documents and have an essential importance for the Commission's appraisal of how the Project is evolving. The beneficiaries will continuously report on the progress of the action (e.g., deliverables, milestones, outputs/outcomes, critical risks, indicators, etc.) in the Portal Continuous Reporting tool and in accordance with the timing and conditions it sets out (as agreed with the granting authority).

Deliverable production

Standardized deliverables (e.g., progress reports not linked to payments, reports on cumulative expenditure, special reports, etc) will be submitted using the templates published on the Portal. Each deliverable tackles a specific task, and must have a task lead who will coordinate the production of the document, interacting as necessary with the other partners involved. Unless agreed otherwise among the partners involved, the WP and task leads are the responsible for the deliverables.

The task lead/WP lead will merge all contributions into a single document. This first draft will then be circulated for a round of comments. Each partner will check its consistency with the plans and give their feedback and approval.

The task/WP lead will then prepare a final draft, which will be sent to the Project Coordinator. The Project Coordinator will normally not enter into the technical merits of the deliverable but will essentially ensure that it is of sufficient quality to be submitted to the EU portal. The Project Manager Officer will format it correctly and make sure all the naming conventions have been followed.

3.2.2 Reporting to the European Commission

Contact with REA office

The project coordinator will keep the REA Project Officer informed about the implementation issues. The project coordinator will contact the REA Project Officer for doubts, questions and details and will discuss problems/changes well in advance.

Reporting

There are two ways of reporting to the EU, continuous and periodic reporting.

1. CONTINUOUS REPORTING

This way of reporting is open all along the project implementation to upload information whenever needed:

- Specific information (e.g., Project summary, Publications, Critical Risks, Open Data etc.)
- Deliverables

2. PERIODIC REPORTING

Automatically open at the end of each reporting period:

- Reporting periods are defined in the Grant Agreement. The BIOTraCes project is organized in three reporting periods:

Reporting Period 1	From M1 to M18
Reporting Period 2	From M19 to M36
Reporting Period 3	From M37 to M48

- Online templates for Periodic Report are available in EU portal-Periodic and Final Reports are the same.

Figure 4: Timeline of reporting during project period, provided by the EU.

The periodic reporting will take place within 60 days after the end of the reporting period. The periodic report consists of:

- 1. Technical report** (part A – structured tables, Part B – free text)
 - activities and tasks implemented per Work Package
 - problems encountered (if any) and explanations and justifications for deviations from GA provisions
 - impact of the project (science, policy, society, economy, etc.)

- annexes: e.g., project logo, diagrams, photographs and videos illustrating the work (if available)

2. Financial report

- financial statements of each beneficiary
- explanation of use of resources and information on subcontracting, in kind contribution
- summary of financial statements.

The final financial report consolidates data from financial statements of all beneficiaries. This report is used for the payment of the final balance of the project.

Funding and tenders portal

EU grants are managed fully electronically through the EU Funding & Tenders Portal ('Portal'). All communications must be made electronically through the Portal, in accordance with the Portal Terms and Conditions and using the forms and templates provided there (except if explicitly instructed otherwise by the granting authority). Communications will be made in writing and clearly identify the grant agreement (project number and acronym) and will be made by persons authorised according to the Portal Terms and Conditions. If the electronic exchange system is temporarily unavailable, instructions will be given on the Portal.

4 COMMUNICATION

4.1 Communication tools for a smooth coordination

The main aim of the communication activities will be to raise awareness, inform and increase visibility of the BIOTraCes project and its solutions to relevant stakeholders and the public at large. This will be done through creating compelling and meaningful content that will convey accessible messages about the project's activities, its results and its implications and benefits. Social media channels (e.g., Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube) and the BIOTraCes website will be used for wide communication, and more specialised channels (e.g., special interest magazines) to reach out to specialists' audiences (e.g., civil society), as well as the local media (e.g., local newspapers, radio and TV) to reach out to end-users and society at large. To achieve these goals, the Table below shows the planned specific communication measure. One key communication measure will be the final video, in which the overall outcome of the project and insights for policy makers are explained.

Sharing Platform

The BIOTraCes website (www.biotraces.eu) will serve as the main public dissemination tool, addressing the public with the project-related content, translated into accessible language; posting original content, videos, and social media campaigns (on LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram). The online presence will be used to develop an online BIOTraCes community of engaged stakeholders and develop a dialogue with them.

The website concerns a public area, containing the following main pages:

- Introduction to Project: BIOTraCes in a Nutshell and BIOTraCes Partners
- Our Principles
- Results: Where (intermediate) results will be displayed
- Actions: Nine case studies explained
- News: Updates about latest news on biodiversity and Social media
- Contact: Project Coordination and Communication

Data Storage/Exchange

To enable uniform and responsible treatment of data in all stages of the project, namely planning, collection, processing, organization and storage, a data management framework will be developed. At the start of the project, a data management plan (DMP) will be created in agreement with all consortium partners, using the template provided by Horizon Europe and which is to be submitted within the first six months. The DMP will be updated throughout the project when new data or other data-significant changes will emerge (e.g., change in consortium policies, composition, etc.).

The project will follow the principle of responsible research and innovation and will comply with The Brussels Declaration: Ethics and Principles for Science & Society Policy-Making, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in all stages of the project, from the research design to the dissemination of the research output.

E-mail exchange and MS Teams SharePoint

Communication between Consortium partners will partly be by e-mail. Agreed is to always write 'BIOTraCes' in the subject of the e-mail to make e-mail recognizable and to increase the findability.

Relevant documents can be found at the MS Teams SharePoint and can be edited by all partners.

5 COLLABORATION

5.1 Working Ethics and responsible behaviour

The working ethics and leadership within the BIOTraCes are open, constructive and coaching in a good work atmosphere. Appropriate behaviour, acceptance of difference, listening and consideration for others is self-evident.

Each person working in BIOTraCEs is committed to responsible behaviour. Responsible and professional behaviour includes responsibility for work and responsibility for interaction. Responsible behaviour is primarily focused on doing our work within the project and interacting with each other. Generally, it means that we:

- perform our own duties responsibly within the given time
- assist and advise others as necessary
- share / convey the necessary information concerning the project
- provide constructive feedback
- are appropriate in interacting with everyone and listening to each other
- take others into account and work constructively with each other
- appreciate diverseness of people and different ways of doing things

All partners are fully committed to promote principles of Gender & Equality Action Plan (GEP) which provides a constructive model to solve concerns, disagreements or any other problems.

5.2 Cooperation

The project coordination leads towards facilitating individual project members and partners taking ownership for activities, but also for the project as a whole. There is an emphasis on working together intensively with the idea in mind that will enable us to also be transformative ourselves. For example, we believe a 'similar' involvement of all research partners in the case studies will enable a better exchange of experiences and learning and positively influence the collaboration between all partners. Moreover, the emphasis of involvement of the societal partners is on the co-production of knowledge on the several layers of analysis, developing and testing of approaches in the case studies. Also, the research partners will all be working together in the other WPs and tasks but with different emphasis and amount of involvement, related to their expertise and preference and the tasks they will carry out during this project.

Project partners share a common vision on the importance of **gender+ in all activities and across all aspects of the project**. Gender+ means we will broaden the gender equality policies in research and innovation to intersections with other potential grounds for discrimination such as ethnicity, disability and sexual orientation. BIOTraCes' Gender+ balance will be continuously supported and monitored by all project partners.